

A holistic approach to snow observations and models in Svalbard (Snow 23)

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1. Introduction

Snow plays a crucial role in Svalbard and significantly impacts ecology and human activity. Ongoing climate change (Isaksen et al., 2022) affects the snow cover and will have even higher impact in the future. Accurate measurements of snow parameters are thus important. Various projects addressing Svalbard's snow cover will give improved measurements of snow parameters, including the essential climate variables (ECVs) snow covered area, snow depth and snow water equivalent¹. This SESS report reviews some of the initiatives, to assess the path forward.

SIOS Snow Pilot² is funded by the Research Council in Norway via SIOS Knowledge Centre in 2022-2023 based on previous SESS report recommendations. It establishes time series of snow cover fraction from satellite sensors and develops three in situ supersites (Figure 1) for snow cover monitoring via standardized time lapse cameras and standardized ground penetrating radar equipment for snow depth and snow water equivalent transects. Despite limited funding, these infrastructures are now largely established, but funding for future continuous operations has not been secured yet.

SIOS SnowInOpt (2023-2024) is funded by SIOS under the infrastructure optimisation call³. The project has four main objectives: 1) Implement

standards for Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) measurements, 2) Carry out GPR measurements, 3) Develop machine learning methods for GPR analysis and 4) develop a prototype method for measuring snow depth in Svalbard using ICESat-2.

The project “Cryosphere Integrated Observation Network on Svalbard” (CRIOS)⁴ focuses on building automatic measuring network on glaciers in Svalbard providing near real-time weather, snow and ice data via the internet. Five glaciers are instrumented.

Figure 1: Map of Svalbard with the 3 current supersites. For data sources see Table 1.

Table 1: Data used to produce Figure 1-3. The datasets have been processed from Level-1 data provided by the satellite ground segments, into geophysical products (snow depth and snow cover fraction) described in section 2. In Figure 2 snow cover is visualized using CVL 3D visualization tools⁵.

Sensor	Organization	Link
Icesat-2 (Figure 1&Figure 2)	NSIDC	https://doi.org/10.5067/ATLAS/ATL03.005 ,
Sentinel-2 (Figure 3)	ESA&EU	https://scihub.copernicus.eu/ , service migrated to https://dataspace.copernicus.eu/ (Nov 1, 2023).

1 WMO <https://gcos.wmo.int/en/essential-climate-variables/snow/ecv-requirements>

2 <https://sios-svalbard.org/SnowPilot2022>

3 <https://sios-svalbard.org/OptimisationCall>

4 <https://sios-svalbard.org/CRIOS>; funded by the EEA Financial Mechanism

5 <https://cvl.eo.esa.int/>

2. The state of the art in snow science

In this section we review relevant snow parameters and observation techniques, as well as models available in Svalbard. Then we review which types of snow-related data are already available in the SIOS data management system, and try to assess the maturity and FAIRness of the datasets.

Snow extent (and snow cover fraction) observed with remote sensing is by far the most mature snow parameter (Dietz et al., 2011). Snow cover is treated separately in the SATMODSNOW report with an update of Malnes et al. (2021) by Vickers et al. (2024). The report focuses on long term time series of snow cover mainly by optical sensors from late 1980 to present and compares with model data for the same period. The findings show a clear need to harmonize models and satellite observations since there are substantial differences. Optical sensors have significantly improved since the start of the satellite era: daily acquisitions with high spatial resolution are now available. There is, however, a need to improve calibration between the different sensors and understand scale differences between the high- and low-resolution sensors. Salzano et al. (2023) in the PASSES report has addressed this issue using time-lapse cameras to calibrate and validate satellite methods. Upcoming work will seek to utilize the variety of spatial scales observed simultaneously to improve results from the past (e.g. reconstructing snow cover in the past at high resolution). In the context of AI-technology we anticipate that correlation with other parameters such as precipitation and temperature can result in high-resolution predictions of the snow cover in the future (Richiardi et al., 2023; Daudt et al., 2023). Other sensors such as Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) can also be utilized to fill gaps in the time-series when optical data are obstructed due to clouds or polar night.

Snow depth has been challenging to measure using satellites. Optical remote sensing can be used via photogrammetric methods and digital elevation models to derive information about snow depth but is challenging due to variable snow properties

(roughness) and poor light conditions and requires high-resolution optical images, mostly limited to airborne surveys (Bührlé et al., 2023). Passive microwave sensors are widely used to estimate snow depth but are currently limited by their relatively low resolution and therefore cannot address areas with high topographic variability (Tanniru et al., 2023). Another approach to derive snow depth from space, is to use satellite altimetry, and in particular laser altimetry. NASA's Ice, Cloud, and land Elevation Satellite-2 (ICESat-2), launched in 2018, carries a laser altimeter that allows for detailed measurements of surface heights with a footprint of ~11 m, and 70 cm sampling interval horizontally along track under cloud-free conditions. During summer, in snow-free areas, ICESat-2 surface heights provide a reference surface in combination with high-resolution digital elevation models. During winter, ICESat-2 senses the snow surface, allowing estimations of snow depth when referenced to snow-free elevations. The SIOS Interoperability project SIOS SnowInOpt aims to develop a processing algorithm to derive snow depth from ICESat-2 measurements. The algorithm uses the geolocated photon height data, in combination with the 2-m resolution Arctic Digital elevation model. We have preliminary results for 2019-2023 in the extended Ny-Ålesund and Adventdalen areas. Figure 2 shows an example of ICESat-2 derived snow depth for Adventdalen, averaged over March/April 2023. We will use field campaign data based on GPR to validate the snow depth estimates. If ICESat-2 snow depth products prove to provide robust snow depth estimates, this can be a high-quality source for snow depth data across Svalbard, and may significantly benefit modelling and upcoming satellite missions that measure snow parameters.

Drone-borne GPR-campaigns have been carried out nearby Longyearbyen for several years during SIOS Infranor. Drone-borne GPR could potentially cover wider areas than GPR on snowmobile (also slopes inaccessible by snowmobile) and also be used to measure snow layer structure and snow

Figure 2: Average snow depth estimates from ICESat-2 in Adventdalen and Sassendalen during March/April 2023. Blue shaded areas indicate glaciers. For data sources see Table 1.

water equivalent. To reduce the current cost of these campaigns, the sensor should be improved/miniaturized to allow more automatic sensing.

In 2022, within the SIOS SnowPilot framework, the first coordinated GPR snow depth surveys in unglaciated areas for calibration of satellite products were conducted using snowmobile. GPR transects around Ny-Ålesund and Hornsund were supplemented with snow depth probing and snow pits for snow water equivalent retrieval. For Hornsund, this was the first use of a High Frequency 1.6 GHz antenna to retrieve snow depth in the shallow snowpack in the tundra.

Snow water equivalent (SWE) is the product of snow depth and snow density and is the third snow-related ECV identified by the World Meteorological Organization (GCOS). This parameter has previously been impossible to measure with sufficient resolution in Svalbard using satellites, whereas on a global scale the results are excellent (CCI-Snow). SWE is measured using passive microwave sensors with coarse resolution unsuitable for mountainous and coastal regions like Svalbard. Ground measurements using standard techniques like bulk density measurements combined with Magnaprobe sensors provide SWE for limited regions. These can also be extended using GPR, and the SIOS project

SnowPilot has established a network of supersites in Ny-Ålesund, Longyearbyen and Hornsund where standardized equipment and measurement protocols will provide at least annual transects that can be used for calibration/validation activities, with the aim to obtain monthly measurements during the winter months.

In addition to transects, continuous point-measurements of SWE are needed to relate temporal variability with the spatial patterns. Up to now, the only site with systematic (every 5 days) time series of manual SWE measurements is the Polish Polar Station Hornsund. Since 2019 a gamma-sensor instrument operates in Ny-Ålesund but could also be deployed at representative sites in Longyearbyen and Hornsund. Other technologies such as snow scales and fibre-optic mats to weigh snow are being considered in SIOS infrastructure proposals. Other promising technology for continuous SWE retrieval is Global Navigation Satellite System interferometric reflectometry (GNSS-IR). In summer 2023, GNSS-IR antennas for the retrieval of snow depth and SWE were installed in Hornsund, Longyearbyen and Ny-Ålesund within CRIOS project.

Upcoming L-band SAR missions (NISAR and ROSE-L) will relatively soon make SWE-retrievals

available at a suitable resolution (< 1 km). NISAR, expected to be launched in 2024, will unfortunately not cover Svalbard, so ROSE-L will be very valuable when launched in 2028. The principle for L-band SAR is to accurately measure the phase change when radar waves penetrate snow cover as compared with snow-free ground (Gunteriusen et al., 2000). The phase change is proportional to SWE. L-band is regarded as much better than C-band (e.g. Sentinel-1) since the radar signal has higher coherency. We expect several initiatives to address SWE using L-band SAR in Svalbard in the coming years.

2.1. Additional snow parameters

In addition to the classical ECVs there is also a need to observe other parameters such as wet snow/liquid water in snow, albedo, snow surface temperature. More complex observations – avalanche activity, snow layering, snow chemistry etc – should also be studied. Wet snow (Vickers et al., 2022) and avalanche activity (Eckerstorfer et al., 2019) are currently monitored in Svalbard and delivered to SIOS DSBM. For some of these fields, both satellite and in situ measurements exist, and could be coordinated in the future.

2.2. Models

A few snow models cover all of Svalbard. In the SATMODSNOW project, the models EBFM (van Pelt et al., 2018) and SeNorge (Saloranta, 2016) were used, but in general the spatial scales are too coarse to capture the dynamics of seasonal snow in Svalbard. Upcoming high-resolution initiatives such as SURFEX/Crocus have been tested for the Ny-Ålesund region (Zweigle et al., 2022) and the CryoGrid model forced by CARRA for all of Svalbard (1991-2020) with 2.5 km resolution (Schmidt et al., 2023). Current models do not really assimilate detailed datasets from remote sensing, and as shown in SATMODSNOW this may result in errors. Long term time series only exist for the snow cover parameter, and not for snow depth

and SWE. Since snow cover is a more qualitative parameter than the others, it is harder to assimilate.

2.3. SIOS Core Data

SIOS has identified the following snow-related core data⁶ (Snow depth, Snow water equivalent, Snow cover and Snow/ice temperature). A search in the SIOS Data Access Portal⁷, based on the description in the meta-data fields, yields a number of datasets (Table 2). It should be noted searches for some of the parameters give many hits, but when the datasets and their meta-data are inspected, we find that the parameter in question is mentioned, although it is not the one being measured. This uncovers a clear need to tag SIOS Core data and a standardised approach to identify variables to avoid erroneous hits in the search procedure. For example, SCD 2.8 includes snow cover data, but some time lapse cameras provide photos, not digitized estimates of snow cover fraction within the camera's field of view (FOV). The FOV should also be defined by a polygon to ease comparison with Earth Observation data.

In addition to more precise dataset tagging, users would benefit from more clarity about a few other information pieces. Table 2 shows that users might need to know whether a dataset is based on model, satellite or in situ data, as well as the dataset's temporal and spatial extent. This is usually a pre-requisite in FAIR data (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). One way to improve the preciseness in the description of the datasets could be to adhere to the Global Change Master (GCMD) keywords⁸.

The approach described above for counting actual snow datasets in the SIOS Data Access Portal can clearly be questioned. Browsing 183 metadata fields opens for errors.

We have also inspected the Cryosphere Virtual Laboratory data portal⁹ which incorporates the SIOS Data Access Portal but has a larger

6 https://sios-svalbard.org/CoreData_Cryosphere

7 <https://sios-svalbard.org/metsis/search>

8 <https://www.earthdata.nasa.gov/learn/find-data/idn/gcmd-keywords>

9 cvl.eo.esa.int/

Table 2: SIOS Core data related to snow. The table was developed by searching the SIOS Data Access Portal for datasets on the Snow Essential Climate Variables (ECVs). We organised the results into different categories based on inspection of individual datasets. Many datasets mention ECVs in the metadata without containing any data on those specific ECVs. This accounts for discrepancy between the number of datasets displayed and the total for the categories in the three rightmost columns.

Parameter SIOS DAP	ID	# datasets displayed	Dataset source		
			Model	Satellite	In situ
Snow cover	SCD 2.8	22	1	5	2
Snow depth	SCD 2.9	64	-	-	37 (*)
Snow water equivalent	SCD 2.10	6	2	-	4
Snow temperature	SCD 2.11	89	-	-	4
Total		183	3	5	47

(*) 9 field campaigns, 13 snow depth time series from meteorological stations, 15 glacier stations

geographical footprint. In general, we find many more snow related datasets here (406 vs. 183), but the chance that the data are not relevant is even higher here partly since many global datasets are not relevant to Svalbard but also since several of the satellite-based datasets do not provide snow ECVs even if these are mentioned in the metadata.

2.4. Digital twins

EU launched the Destination earth (DestinE) framework¹⁰ in 2023 which aims at developing a highly accurate digital model of the entire earth. The model will monitor, simulate, and predict interrelations between natural phenomena and human activity using accurate earth observation data, high-performance computers and models, and artificial intelligence. The ambitions are clearly

high, and though it is unclear how an accurate model will be achieved, this type of EU ambition pushes the scientific community to utilize the infrastructure and methods being developed. The snow community in Svalbard has already started to prepare digital twins (Figure 3), and several have been submitted to address snow and other components of the cryosphere (sea ice, glacier, permafrost). The vision is a holistic approach where models and observations interact in real-time and are able to assimilate past and current observations using AI-technology to recognize the detailed patterns and interrelations between large scale meteorological phenomena and small scale differences in the snow cover on the ground. Climate simulations could also be involved to make detailed predictions about snow cover in the future.

Figure 3: Left: Concept design for a digital twin for the water cycle in Svalbard. Right: 3D Visualization of the snow cover in Longyearbyen on June 1, 2020 and June 1, 2100. The first is based on Sentinel-2 data, whereas the last is inferred from time-series of Sentinel-2 (2016-2022) and a climate scenario. For data sources see Table 1.

¹⁰ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/destination-earth>

3. Contributions to interdisciplinarity

Snow is an important part of the extended water cycle. The water cycle is highlighted in the SESS Synthesis report (Christensen et al., 2023) as the most important earth system research component integrating interdisciplinarity across most of the spheres (atmosphere, hydrosphere, cryosphere, ecosphere). Combining skills from the observation community and the modelling community is necessary to obtain a holistic approach to snow

science in Svalbard and improve the snow parameterizations. Collaborations with other disciplines, across the spheres, but also with social and health scientists could also be achieved by joining forces, e.g. in projects related to geohazards like snow avalanches, using drones to study polar bear dens and study relations between rain-on-snow events and lichen as reindeer forage.

4. Unanswered questions

This chapter incorporates some of the recommendations from two chapters in the current SESS report (Vickers et al., 2024; Salzano et al., 2024). Based on this and work carried out in several snow-related projects we recommend that the snow community within SIOS continue the good collaboration to improve observations and

modelling of the snow cover and approach the field holistically, e.g. by establishing a digital twin for the water cycle in Svalbard. The community should also seek collaboration with leading research groups in Europe to address fundamental scientific questions like how the water cycle can be closed in Svalbard and how this links to global Earth System Science.

5. Summary

The snow community within SIOS works systematically to address a variety of snow parameters with a goal to obtain as accurate and detailed observations of snow as possible, and to share them as FAIR data in the SIOS data management system. Snow cover extent is a mature parameter where many time-series exist, but we notice that harmonization and inter-calibration is still needed. Snow depth and snow water

equivalent will soon be observable from space, providing even more quantitative measurements of terrestrial snow that could be useful for our total understanding. However, there is also need for extended ground observations for calibration and validation. Models and digital twins need to develop assimilation strategies that can capture the information contained in in situ and remote sensing data of the snow cover.

6. Joint recommendations

- Intercomparisons (and intercalibrations) of snow products from coarse scale (4 km, AVHRR), via medium scale (500 m, MODIS) and detailed (10–20 m, S2-MSI) to sub-meter scale (time-lapse cameras) should continue and be used to improve remotely-sensed data products across all spatial scales.
- The SIOS supersites for remote sensing of snow must be continued as a reference for upcoming satellite products and snow parameter retrieval methods. Funding of snow water equivalent transects using GPR and web-camera operations should be sought from available sources.
- Attempts should be made to map, harvest and maintain (if possible) all kinds of Earth Observation products of snow over the archipelago and validate/quantify errors in each of the datasets. Possible new sensors are VIIRS (500 m), Landsat-8 (30 m) and Planet Labs (4 m).
- The assimilation of Earth Observation data in snow hydrology and snow process models needs to be further investigated. The CryoGrid model (2.5 km) should be included.
- A digital twin framework for snow cover in Svalbard should be implemented to assimilate data in models using AI-concepts, and possibly make future predictions about the snow cover.

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Taking a snow profile in a mountain slope. (Photo: Eirik Malnes)